

Short Communication

OF REJECT

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Abstract

Single father suffers. He may leave the children at ease since he lacks in motherly affection. Single mother suffers more in the patriarchal society. Misfortune dogs her wherever she goes. Such a mother has to bear the social dogma till she breathes her last. Yet she does not lap less her children. This is the outcome of rejection. It is the rejection of humanity.

Key words: Reject, dismiss, unacceptable, faulty, inadequate, unacceptable, refuse

Introduction

Creative writing is based more on manifestation rather than on expression. It does not inform, rather it reveals. So it bears no reference. The best creative writing is critical, and the best critical writing is creative. This article is an outcome of thinking about creative writing meant for a general readership. As such, I have adopted a free style methodology so that everyone can enjoy the pleasure of reading. As you might know, Francis Bacon (1561-1626), the immortal essayist, wrote many essays namely 'Of Love', 'Of Friendship', 'Of Ambition', 'Of Studies', and so on. The multiple-minded genius correctly pointed out that all the words of the dictionary can be used as themes for essays. But little has been done since his death to continue or finish his monumental task. Bacon's unique individual style of presentation ignited my imagination and encouraged me to write creative essays as a method of relieving a wide range of emotions through catharsis.

ARTICLE

Reject is to dismiss as inadequate, unacceptable, or faulty. For example: Union negotiators rejected a 1.5 per cent pay award.

It is a person or thing dismissed as inadequate or unacceptable. For example: Some of the team's rejects have gone on to prove themselves in championships.

It is to refuse to accept, use, or believe something or someone. For example: The appeal was rejected by the court.

It is to not give someone the love and attention they want and are expecting from you. For example: When she was sent to boarding school, she felt as though her parents had rejected her.

From medical point of view if body rejects an organ that has been put in during a medical operation, it fails to accept it and tries to attack and destroy it.

It is a product that is damaged or not perfectly made.

It is a person who has not been accepted by an organization or by society.

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For example: He considered himself to be one of life's rejects.

If someone is rejected then he considers himself as scrap. A sentimental soul becomes much upset. Sometimes he commits suicide. In contrast an intelligent person tries to find out the cause of rejection. He takes precautionary measures so that second time rejection does not occur again and proceeds accordingly to realise the desired result. An ambitious person tries repeatedly till he wins the battle.

A wise never finds fault with others. He finds faults with himself. The learned contends that to find fault with others is merely wastage of time. It is beneficial to rectify self. If liability is imposed upon him illegally, he leaves that association without creating further trouble. He knows good company pays, bad company pains.

Rejection causes wastage of money, property, place and time as well. As such they say look before you leap.

Someone selects. Someone rejects. They are diagonally opposite regarding philosophy towards their lives. Someone rejects considering no compromise with quality. Someone rejects intentionally to enjoy sadistic pleasure. He wants to fix liability upon others keeping him safe and secure.

He who selects is optimist and positive in nature. He who rejects is pessimist and possesses negative attitude always. He is detrimental to the society for his derogative thinking. He does not know or does not want to know the talent and time required for selection. It is a tough job. It is a time consuming job. Much patience is required for any selection considering all controlling parameters.

In any employment when number of applicants are more than the vacancies then interview stands for elimination rather than selection. Generally selection is done against 5:1 ratio. In case of greater numbers of elimination the interviewers have to be more merciless to prepare the final list.

Rejection is easy; selection is difficult like destruction and construction

respectively. Both are concluded basing on various parameters. If they are based on logic then it is O.K. If they are based on emotion then there lies the problem.

As per physics the metal which is heated quickly becomes cold quickly. Similarly, if a person chooses someone easily, rejects that very person quickly. In both the cases if positive traits are not considered judiciously then negative traits surface later on. Similarly, if complexion is the sole criterion then other characteristics should be ignored. Because a person cannot possess all the qualities equally. Absence or lacking in any other quality should not be the cause or because of rejection. Then it is called whimsicality and tyranny.

A whimsical person accepts someone in the morning. He rejects that very person in the evening of that very day. He again accepts another new one and rejects in the same style. This is an endless episode of an infinite drama. Thus his mood and motive are gloriously so uncertain. Whether mood controls him or he controls mood is a million dollar question. Love at first sight ignores everything. He chooses her. He is hungry. As such he hears none, cares nobody and dares never. Then it is difficult for him to reject the fiancée.

An innocent girl believes and becomes involved easily. She does not and cannot reject due to lacking in experience. A deserted woman is cautious to accept a stranger. She believed someone in the past and was betrayed later on. Thus she has become more cautious than a new one. She does not want to be deceived further thereby rejected second time.

Everybody wants to avoid rejection. But none can escape from it. Reject offers lesson. It helps to rectify. It helps to be cautious.

Rejection sometimes disheartens. Sometimes it ignites desire. Both are personality traits. Personality pattern of concerned someone is disclosed from such unique outcome.

Rejection is omnipresent. Man faces it. He has to face it. He is bound to face it. Whether man likes it or not it matters little. Rejection bothers not or cares none at all. Thus man willy-nilly faces rejection in its various forms and features having different degrees and dimensions as well. Reject is quite democratic in its nature and behaviour. Rich or poor, literate or illiterate, aristocrat or down-trodden i.e., people from all walks of life are equal and at par to it. It levels all and everybody with its violent force.

Different persons reject differently. The rejection of wise sharply differs with a fool. A fool rejects which one is to accept and accepts which one is to reject thereby loses both ways. A wise does not reject different thing, he rejects differently. It is really an art.

Both acceptance and rejection if are done basing on logic then it is beneficial. If they are done ignoring logic then both are liable to loss. He who accepts is an optimist. An optimist is positive in nature. He always accelerates. He inspires. He sees light everywhere. He dwells in light. He escorts from dark to light.

He who rejects is a pessimist. He is a negative person. He causes retardation. He feels inward pull. So he disheartens someone who seeks his advice. He enjoys sadistic pleasure.

If a genuine person is deprived and a corrupted person is engaged in any establishment then the firm suffers from two angles. Firstly, the corrupted person steals and earns illegally. Secondly, he cannot take right decision due to his callousness. Thus the firm suffers from double destruction. Darkness accelerates. Rejection culminates.

Rejection is a negative force. Everybody is afraid of it more or less. Examination is alias and akin to phobia. The students are the most sufferers of it. Both good and bad students are afraid of it. A bad student fears it more. To do anything or to face anything stamina is a must. Stamina is alias and akin to courage. Courage is not culture free. It cannot conquer all, everything and everywhere. A sharp knife can cut anything. Fire can burn anything. A courageous person can do one job. He may not perform another job. He is selected for one job. He is rejected for another job.

All jobs are not for all. A murderer can murder at ease. He is hired to murder. He cannot face any interview board for any job. He is rejected. In contrast, a brilliant student can face any tough interview board. He is selected for the job. He cannot murder. He is afraid of blood. He is not suitable for that job. He is rejected.

All cannot stage the roll of king. Similarly, always stage make up may not be possible. Right man in the wrong place is quite useless. His candidature is rejected.

Instant rejection is better than the late rejection being the long awaited outcome. Instant failure enables an entrepreneur to search for new avenue. If the result is uncertain, yet someone hopes for success but ultimately if he is rejected then his future success becomes a big question.

Waiting should be time bound. It is not wise to wait for the uncertain period of time. Breakfast should be taken in time whatever someone gets in the morning. One should not wait till noon for better meal. If it is taken in the noon it is no more breakfast. Similarly, dinner cannot be called lunch. Then the person suffers from indigestion. It causes health hazards. A health conscious person is alert for time. He takes food timely. He does not wait. He rejects better food of late hours. To him a bird in hand is better two in the bush.

Someone likes to do all his jobs during day time. Both acceptance and rejection will be as per day schedule. With the sun set he closes his activities. He awaits next sun rise. He rejects night duty for its dark side. An optimist thinks always for success. A pessimist always thinks for failure. He always mentally fails before doing any job. If an optimist is rejected then he explains his failure as waiting of better chance. Rejection opens future opening.

Lovers love each other. They reject each other. They depart each other. Till now there is no problem. Problem lies elsewhere. The children become the prey of rejection. Both leave them. They are dumped into the orphan house. The orphan houses become over crowded by these rejected human babes. These children are deprived from mother's affection. Unguarded childhood coupled with unshaded infant render them prodigal. In future, such a grown up child does suffer from identity crisis.

Single father suffers. He may leave the children at ease since he lacks in motherly affection. Single mother suffers more in the patriarchal society. Misfortune dogs her wherever she goes. Such a mother has to bear the social dogma till she breathes her last. Yet she does not lap less her children. This is the outcome of rejection. It is the rejection of humanity.

There are two types of persons. The first category if be rejected tries repeatedly till he wins. The second category if be rejected leaves the battle permanently and tries not further. Sometimes such a sentimental soul commits suicide. Now he who commits suicide does not have important information regarding life. He is well advised that a frustrated person should not commit suicide since life has its sweet side too.

Rejection means failure. All cannot bear the shock of defeat. In any competitive examination there are various types of competitors viz., 1st

attempt, 2nd attempt, 3rd attempt and so on. He who cracks in the first chance is really brilliant. All are not brilliant. All cannot be brilliant. All are not destined to be brilliant. This answers why geniuses are numbered who really crack in the first attempt. They are not rejected. They cannot be rejected. The word rejection is absent in their dictionary.

It is obvious that less talented persons may not pass in the first chance. One should not lose heart seeing others around him in the examination hall. He may think that the one who passes, passes as per his turn which may be 1st chance, 2nd chance, 3rd chance and so on. In near future his turn must come.

Now whenever someone tries for something there are two possibilities. Either the person may fail or the person may fail to fail. A judicious person should simply try for the second option. The person should think that he

does not belong to the past days but to the noons of the bright and golden future. He must be positive. He must be an optimist. Sometimes one rejection takes place since a better option waits. This is the essence of rejection.

CONCLUSION

Long hope if he is rejected pains much. Similar is the long relation. As such before growing any hope or relation one should be careful regarding its feasibility. They say ability without feasibility implies disability. In most of the cases of human life this is the cause and because of rejection.

REFERENCES

No reference, since the present article is an outcome of Creative Nonfiction Writing.

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